

DIELECTRIC NON-DESTRUCTIVE EXAMINATION OF AGEING OF ADHESIVELY BONDED STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the use of Dielectric Spectroscopy as a non-destructive method for monitoring, firstly solvent ingress at elevated temperatures within aluminium adhesively bonded joints and secondly water uptake within carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) bonded joints. Dielectric measurements were carried out in both frequency and time domain, allowing for changes in the dielectric permittivity and loss to be calculated. Frequency domain analysis allows the effect of solvent ingress in the bondline to be assessed, whereas time domain analysis allows for the identification of irregularities found within the bondline. CFRP samples, in addition to ageing, have been subjected to thermal spiking at cryogenic temperatures at regular intervals throughout the ageing period. Destructive mechanical tests, Mode 1 and Mode 2, were also carried out on the aluminium and CFRP samples and a correlation with dielectric measurements obtained. The dielectric permittivity and loss were found to increase throughout the ageing period whereas the mechanical strength of the joints was reduced, in some cases quite dramatically as a result of leaching of the adhesive by the solvents. Time domain (TDR) analysis has also shown the presence of defects within the bondline of the joint structures.

Keywords: dielectric spectroscopy, non-destructive testing, adhesively bonded joints, CFRP and solvent ingress.

INTRODUCTION

The use of structural adhesives, for engineering applications, has increased dramatically in recent years due to the many advantages associated with their use, such as; increased strength, uniform stress distribution, improved aerodynamics, reduced weight and simpler and cheaper component construction [1-3]. Aluminium bonded structures have been used as primary structural aircraft components for many years as a result of advances made in the surface pre-treatment of the metal. Pre-treatments provide better environmental stability against the effects of hot/moist environments as well as promoting the development of stronger bonds to polymeric materials [4].

During the service lifetime of adhesively bonded structures, the environmental conditions these structures are exposed to can adversely affect their performance. Hot/moist environments are most damaging to adhesively bonded structures necessitating the development of non-destructive methods for the assessment of their quality and integrity. There are many non-destructive techniques in current use; ultrasonic, radiography, Fokker bond test, etc. However no non-destructive test exists for measurement of the moisture content in an adhesively bonded joint. In fact most non-destructive techniques are aimed at detecting cracks, voids, porosity or lack of adhesive [5].

Dielectric spectroscopy has been developed, over the last ten years, for the non-destructive evaluation of aluminium and CFRP bonded joints. Details of the measurement technique and theory have been presented elsewhere [6, 7, 8]. This type of evaluation has been proven to be highly sensitive to ingress of moisture within the bonded joints due to the high permittivity of water and is the basis of this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

In this study aluminium adhesively bonded joints were manufactured using series 2000 MTL Spec L166 alloy (Cu, Mg, Si) supplied by British Aerospace plc, Prestwick, UK. Chromic acid anodised pre-treatment was carried out on the aluminium producing an oxide film of roughly 400 nm. The CFRP adherents were manufactured from unidirectional carbon fibre pre-impregnated film, trade named 914C-TS-5-34 supplied by Hexcel Composites. The adherends were laid up in the following sequence $[90_2/0/90_2/0/90]_S$ to give symmetric bi-directional laminates and cured at 170°C for 1 hour. A pressure of 7 bars was applied to consolidate the laminate. Aluminium joints had a bondline thickness of 0.2 mm (one layer of adhesive) whereas the CFRP joints had a bondline thickness of 1 mm (6 layers of adhesive).

The adhesive used was a structural epoxy system, supplied by 3M, and designated Scotch-Weld Brand AF 163-2K. The joint structures were autoclave cured at a temperature of 125⁰C under a pressure of 2 bars for 1 hour.

Prior to ageing the joints were dielectrically tested, to ensure a high standard of joint was manufactured. The joints were then divided into those that would be tested non-destructively and those that would be tested destructively at given intervals over the ageing period. The aluminium joints were aged in a variety of solvents commonly encountered by aircraft, at a temperature of 65⁰C which included; de-ionised water, simulated ocean water (ASTM: D 1141-90), AVTUR F-34 (military aviation fuel), OM18 DEF STAN 91-48/1 (hydraulic fluid), ethylene glycol (anti-icing agent), urea solution and dichloromethane (paint strippers). The dichloromethane was studied at room temperature due to flash point hazards. All samples were aged in round-bottomed flasks fitted with reflux condensers and heated by a common oil bath. The CFRP joints were aged at 75⁰C in de-ionised water, and held in a standard water bath. These were exposed to cryogenic temperatures at regular intervals throughout the ageing period.

Dielectric measurements were carried out in reflection mode over the frequency range 300 kHz to 3 GHz using a Hewlett Packard 8753A Network analyser. The system was calibrated using three independent standards whose reflection coefficients are known over the frequency range of interest: short, open and a matched load at 50 Ω . Dielectric measurements were performed at low frequencies, 0.1 Hz to 63 kHz, using the Strathdown Dielectric Spectrometer.

In addition, destructive mechanical tests were conducted. Mode II shear testing was based on the ASTM 3807-93-Strength properties of adhesives in peel by tension loading. A Zwick tensile testing machine was used to apply a crosshead separation rate of 1.27 mm/minute for shear testing

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section the results of the solvent uptake study on aluminium bonded joints will be reviewed followed by the results for the water uptake / freezing of the CFRP joints.

Solvent ageing: aluminium joints

As mentioned, aluminium bonded joints were exposed to a variety of solvents and therefore, were degraded to different degrees depending on the solvent. The results presented here will focus in detail on only three of these environments, dichloromethane, de-ionised water and sea-water, although

reference will be made to each of the remaining solvents. Figure 1 details the dielectric permittivity and loss for three of the systems monitored during this study. Before discussing these results it should be noted that ageing in common aviation fluids like hydraulic fluid, aviation fuel and propylene glycol did not lead to significant deviations in the dielectric permittivity or loss, although the presence of the solvents did result in increased values at lower frequencies as a result of electrode polarization and ionic conductivity.

From Figure 1 (top) it can be seen that immersion of aluminium joints in dichloromethane at room temperature led to an increase in the permittivity during the first few days' exposure, consistent with the ingress of the highly polar molecules. Subsequent to this point however, the permittivity can be seen to decrease quite dramatically as the dichloromethane molecules swell the polymeric network leading to leaching of the un-reacted monomer units and ultimately degradation of the epoxy adhesive. The high permittivity values at low frequencies can be attributed to the generation of a charged double layer of MWS processes. The loss data shows similar behaviour at low frequencies consistent with ionic conduction processes and possible void formation. At higher frequencies however no significant changes occur.

Considering now the permittivity plot for the joints aged in de-ionised water, Figure 1 (middle), there is a steady increase associated with the continued ageing of the joints. This increase in permittivity is consistent with an augmentation in the number of water molecules present within the adhesive matrix. This is also reflected in the loss data at high frequencies, which shows a distinct rise with exposure time. Again at lower frequencies the higher values for both the permittivity and the loss are attributed to various conduction processes associated with the presence of water within the joint structure. A similar result was observed for the joints aged in urea, although the dielectric permittivity indicated a higher water content, possibly due to the urea acting as a plasticiser, swelling the matrix and allowing a greater volume of water to penetrate the matrix.

Finally by looking at the sea-water plots it can be seen that initially there is an increase in the permittivity again due to the ingress of water, however the data then begin to exhibit a decrease caused by a widening of the bondline as a result of salt deposition followed by the hydration of the surface oxide layer to hydroxide. A relaxation feature is apparent on both plots at about 10 kHz, which has been attributed to hydration of the oxide. The dramatic values present at the low frequency end of the spectrum for both plots can be attributed to various conduction processes and corrosion of the aluminium substrate.

Figure 1 3D plots showing the dielectric permittivity and loss for aluminium joints exposed to three environments, dichloromethane, de-ionised water and simulated ocean water, top, middle and bottom respectively.

Figure 2 details the time domain data, presented as waterfall plots, for the three ageing environments. From this it can be seen that ageing in dichloromethane resulted in a displacement of the positive peaks towards longer response times, indicating an increase in the dielectric permittivity. Following on from this it can be seen that the positive peaks then began to move back towards shorter response times as the study continued. This is in agreement with the frequency domain data. Of interest is the increase in peak amplitude of the positive peaks towards the end of the study; this can be related to the energy input in the system, leaching of the adhesive and degradation of the adhesive. As the un-reacted product is leached from the adhesive the electrical signal is able to propagate through the joint to a greater extent. Joints aged in de-ionised water and sea-water show a displacement of the positive peaks to longer response times, again indicative of an increase in the permittivity due to an increase in the number of water molecules present in the joint structure.

Figure 2 Time domain data, shown as waterfall plots, for joints aged in (a) dichloromethane, (b) de-ionised water and (c) sea-water.

The absence of any additional reflections around the zero amplitude regions of the de-ionised water trace, Figure 2 (b), suggests that no voids or disbands have occurred at this stage. The trace for the sea-water aged joints, Figure 2 (c), shows a slight displacement of the positive peaks to shorter response times after 390 days ageing, indicated by the blue line, suggesting a decrease in the permittivity. Subsequent traces show differences in the peak amplitude and shape for the first positive peak suggesting changes in joint geometry or structural integrity. There are additional shoulders present on the peaks implying the presence of voids within the joint structure. The imperfection of the final trace, measured after 630 days (given by a red line) reflects the fact that the joints at this stage in the study have fallen apart.

Mechanical results: aluminium joints

Figure 3 details the shear strength profiles for aluminium joints exposed to 7 different ageing environments. From the plots it can be seen that ageing in aviation fuel, hydraulic fluid and propylene glycol did not significantly decrease the shear strength after 730 days (132 on the time axis). In contrast however, joints exposed to dichloromethane showed a dramatic drop in shear strength after only 50 days (50 on the time axis). This is consistent with the results obtained from dielectric measurements. The shear strength profiles for joints exposed to water-based environments show almost identical losses in shear strength during the first 100 days, which is attributed to the interaction of the water molecules with the polymer matrix. Joints exposed to sea-water and de-ionised water exhibit a recovery in strength, whereas joints exposed to urea show a continued decrease in strength with ageing time. A similar trend is observed for Mode I testing.

Figure 3 Average shear strength as a function of ageing time for joints exposed to a variety of environments commonly encountered by aircraft.

CFRP ageing

In this section results will be presented for carbon fibre composite joints exposed to de-ionised water at 75°C and systematically spiked to -20°C. Spiking to cryogenic temperatures occurred once a week with the joints exposed for a period of 24 hours. Figure 4 details the dielectric permittivity and loss profiles for these CFRP joints. In both cases the permittivity is seen to increase with exposure time indicating an increase in the number of water molecules within the joint structure. A similar trend is observed for the loss data at high frequencies, suggesting an increase in the free water within the system. The joints that have been exposed to -20°C exhibit higher permittivity and loss values at lower frequencies. This is related to the amount of water present within the adhesive and various conduction processes taking place within the joint structures.

Figure 4 3D plots showing dielectric permittivity and loss for CFRP joints aged in de-ionised water at 75°C (top) and 75°C then exposed to -20°C (bottom).

Considering now the time domain data for both systems, presented in Figure 5, it can be seen that as ageing progresses (unaged trace shown at the top) the positive peaks are displaced to longer response times. This is consistent with an increase in the dielectric permittivity of the adhesive due to water ingress. The broadening of the peaks and the reduction in peak amplitude are suggestive of a change in impedance within the system. Additional reflections around the zero amplitude regions (indicated by a red arrow on the unaged trace) can be seen to be increasing in amplitude with ageing time (shown by arrows on the final trace). The additional reflections indicate the presence of voids, whereas the increase in amplitude suggests the voids are growing in size. Further peaks become evident as the first positive peak shifts towards longer response times, again indicating the onset of void formation.

Figure 5 Time domain traces for CFRP joints aged at (a) 75°C and (b) 75°C then exposed to -20°C. Ageing time progresses from top to bottom.

Table 1 highlights the variation in the shear stress and engineering strain with progressive ageing. The data presented here concerns only the joints aged in de-ionised water then exposed to cryogenic temperatures. From this it can be seen that there is a steady decrease in both parameters associated with water penetrating the adhesively bonded structure. Failure of the dry, unaged joints is cohesive within the adhesive layer, which upon ageing progresses to the interface, where after more than 4000 hours failure occurs at the adherend /adhesive interface. The loss in strength during the early stages of ageing can be attributed to plasticisation of the epoxy adhesive due to swelling of the matrix, caused by water breaking the interchain bonds in adjacent polymer chains and forming hydrogen

bonds. However, continued hygrothermal activity within the composite adherends appears to have led to delamination of the fibre / adhesive interface.

Ageing Time (h)	Maximum Stress (MPa)	Loss in Stress (%)	Ultimate Strain	Loss in Strain (%)
0	27.69 ± 1.9	0	0.077 ± 0.0028	0
840	19.15 ± 0.8	-30.8	0.065 ± 0.0022	-15.8
1680	14.97 ± 1.0	-45.9	0.052 ± 0.0037	-31.8
4200	12.68 ± 0.5	-54.2	0.049 ± 0.0012	-36.2

Table 1 Variation of the maximum stress and ultimate engineering strain as a function of exposure time

CONCLUSIONS

The paper has demonstrated that Dielectric Spectroscopy can be used as a non-destructive method for monitoring solvent ingress at elevated temperature in aluminium adhesively bonded joints. Also that water uptake in CFRP joints can be monitored by this method as well.

For the aluminium joints it was shown that exposure of the joints to pain-strippers (dichloromethane) had the most deleterious effect. In addition exposure to water environment led to a larger decrease in mechanical properties than other fluids studied.

For the CFRP joints water penetration led to a continuing decrease in the mechanical properties. This was due initially to plasticisation effects but later to delamination of the fibre/adhesive interface.

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